

Exploring Generative AI for Citation Context Typing

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Abstract: This study explores integrating generative AI to enhance citation context typing. Using Claude LLM, we generate synthetic data aligned with the Citation Typing Ontology (CiTO) to train a classifier. This supervised learning experiment involves training a classifier to identify citation types using this synthetic data. We evaluate the classifier's performance on uncategorised citation statements. Additionally, we extend our analysis to test the classifier trained on English language citation context statements on statements extracted from Swedish and German research publications. A novel aspect of this work lies in the fusion of bibliometrics and experimental work in semantic modelling, employing language models to train machine learning models for research content evaluation. While acknowledging the inherent limitations of machine learning algorithms, we propose further testing using real-time scenarios and human evaluators. This study aims to push the boundaries of research methodology by integrating generative AI beyond text generation into the research process itself.

1. Introduction

Integrating semantic modelling techniques in bibliometric research methodology allows us to explore and understand scholarly data. This study combines semantic modelling and citation context analysis, using generative AI to enhance classification. Our approach focuses on employing Large Language Models (LLMs), specifically Claude LLM, to generate synthetic data aligned with the Citation Typing Ontology (CiTO) (see Peroni & Shotton, 2012).

Studies of citation functions of references (Moravcsik & Murugesan, 1975; Chubin & Moitra, 1975; Spiegel-Rösing, 1977) or the citation context (Small & Greenlee, 1980) are generally performed manually, but automatic supervised methods were introduced by Teufel et al. (2006). An overview of using semi-automatic and automatic methods for citation context typing can be found in Ding et al. (2014). Recently, such approaches have been commercialised (e.g., Scite.ai), and a search for +“automatic” +“citation context analysis” in Dimensions.ai yields more than 400 hits. Synthetic citation data to evaluate classifier performance seems scarce in the literature. The only examples we have found are Gupta et al. (2023), who used GPT-2 to generate a sample citation context dataset, and Zhang et al. (2023), who extended the technique.

2. Methodology

This study aims to investigate the classification performance of LLM-based content representation for the classification of citation types in a collection of citation statements. We used synthetic data produced by a large language model for the training and initial evaluation of the trained classifier. More specifically, a collection of $n = 432$ citation statements (initially specified as $n = 450$, although the model failed to generate the total number of statements for some categories) distributed over nine citation types (see Table 1), selected from the CiTO framework, were generated by prompting the Claude (claude-3-sonnet-20240229) large language model.

We first instructed the model to act as a researcher, citing previous literature. To make the citation statements more varied, we added the instruction that it could put the reference in different positions in the citing sentence:

Prompt:

You are a researcher in different research fields. Please generate sentences containing a reference [X] using academic language. Sometimes the sentence starts with the reference, sometimes it has the reference in the end and sometimes it is in the middle of the sentence.

For each of the nine different citation types, we instructed the LLM to generate 50 citation statements using the description of each citation type in CiTO using a sentence starting with “Please generate 50 citation statements where the citing entity...” (Table 1):

Table 1. Selected citation types from CiTO

authority	...cites the cited entity as one that provides an authoritative description or definition of the subject under discussion.
cited as related	...cites the cited entity as one that is related.
confirms	...confirms facts, ideas or statements presented in the cited entity.
critiques	...critiques statements, ideas or conclusions presented in the cited entity.
data source	.. cites the cited entity as source of data.
disputes	...disputes statements, ideas or conclusions presented in the cited entity.
potential solution	...cites the cited entity as providing or containing a possible solution to the issues being discussed.
recommended reading	...cited entity as an item of recommended reading.
uses conclusions from	...describes work that uses conclusions presented in the cited entity.

The generated statements were characterised by a format as exemplified by the following generated statements (one each from the 50 variants) for each citation type (Table 2).

Table 2. Generated statements from the model

authority	“[48] offers an authoritative description of ““emotional intelligence,”” which encompasses the ability to recognize, understand, manage, and reason with emotions in oneself and others.”
confirms	As suggested in [15], the proposed model accurately captures the observed phenomena.
critiques	The conclusions drawn in [26] regarding the effectiveness of the intervention are not fully justified by the results.
data source	The data on renewable energy production were obtained from the reports cited in [29].
disputes	Our findings challenge the assumptions and premises upon which the theoretical model proposed in [X] is based.
potential solution	18. A promising solution to the problem of deforestation is discussed in [X], where the authors introduce a sustainable forestry management approach.
recommended reading	[27] is highly recommended for its interdisciplinary approach.
related	13. As noted by [X], the choice of parameters can significantly influence the outcome of the analysis.
uses conclusions from	[36] offers a compelling perspective on the ethical considerations surrounding artificial intelligence, which we incorporate into our analysis.

As noted, the LLM interpreted the instructions inconsistently; sometimes numbered each statement and sometimes added the “x” as instructed in the prompt. In some cases, each citation statement was numbered in an ordered list. We did not modify the generated data but used it as the Claude LLM produced it.

These citation statements were used as training data for automated classification using the support vector machine (SVM) algorithm with a linear kernel. In preparation for the automated classification, the statements were embedded (vectorised) using a multilingual embedding model within the SentenceTransformers framework (see Reimers & Gurevych, 2019), resulting in 384-dimensional document vectors. 70 % of the data was allocated as training data and the remainder as test data. The resulting classification performance was evaluated using the standard macro-average recall, precision, and F1 measures and a confusion matrix. The trained classifier was also tested and manually evaluated in an external dataset of statements sampled from English, Swedish, and German research publications.

3. Results

To estimate the potential of sentence embeddings for separating the citation type categories in the representation space, we used the t-SNE algorithm (see van der Maaten & Hinton, 2008) to visualise the citation statement embeddings. This algorithm maps the original representation space to vector space of low dimensionality (typically $dim = 2$) while aiming to preserve the original metric topology as closely as possible. The resulting visualisation is displayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Visualisation of the citation statement embeddings using t-SNE

The resulting classification performance using sentence embeddings and the SVM algorithm is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Classification performance over the nine citation types, together with macro-average scores

citation type	recall	precision	F ₁
confirms	0.933	1.000	0.966
disputes	0.929	1.000	0.963
critiques	1.000	1.000	1.000
uses conclusions from	0.943	0.943	0.943
authority	0.971	0.971	0.971
data source	0.914	0.970	0.941
potential solution	1.000	1.000	1.000
recommended reading	1.000	0.946	0.972

cited as related	1.000	0.897	0.946
macro-average	0.967	0.969	0.967

As can be observed in Table 2, the classification performance is generally high for all the citation type categories, with a few categories obtaining an F_1 score of 1.0. Performance variations could be due to multiple factors. These could be based on ambiguity in describing a distinct type or similarities between different types since we only assign one class to each statement (single label classification). Some citation types might be more direct, while others are more indirect and present a more tentative role. This analysis is complemented by the information provided in the confusion matrices in Figure 2 and Figure 3., showing the extent to which the classifier has mutually mixed up the categories. That ‘data source’ and ‘uses conclusions from’ are confused is quite intuitive, and the same could be said about statements that are each other’s antonyms: ‘confirms’ and ‘disputes’, which are related to the relatively neutral statement type ‘related’.

Figure 2. Confusion matrix for the classification performance, raw frequencies

		Predicted										
		authority	confirm	critiques	data source	disputes	potential solution	recommended reading	related	uses conclusions from		Σ
Actual	authority	34	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	35
	confirm	0	28	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	30
	critiques	0	0	35	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	35
	data source	0	0	0	32	0	0	0	1	0	2	35
	disputes	0	0	0	0	26	0	0	0	2	0	28
	potential solution	0	0	0	0	0	35	0	0	0	0	35
	recommended reading	0	0	0	0	0	0	35	0	0	0	35
	related	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	35	0	0	35
	uses conclusions from	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	33	35
	Σ	35	28	35	33	26	35	37	39	35		303

Figure 3. Confusion matrix for the classification performance, row percentages

		Predicted										
		authority	confirm	critiques	data source	disputes	potential solution	recommended reading	related	uses conclusions from		Σ
Actual	authority	97.1 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	2.7 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	35
	confirm	0.0 %	100.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	5.1 %	0.0 %	30
	critiques	0.0 %	0.0 %	100.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	35
	data source	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	97.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	2.7 %	0.0 %	5.7 %	35
	disputes	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	100.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	5.1 %	0.0 %	28
	potential solution	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	100.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	35
	recommended reading	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	94.6 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	35
	related	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	89.7 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	35
	uses conclusions from	2.9 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	3.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	94.3 %	35
	Σ	35	28	35	33	26	35	37	39	35		303

To explore the predictive power of the model trained on synthetic citation context statements, we selected several sentences containing references from articles in biochemistry, theoretical philosophy, political science, and scientometrics. Additionally, we provisionally included citation statements from a multilingual context. These were a study in education science in Swedish and a German social science article. Examples of the outcomes are shown in Table 4. Based on the model predictions, we got agreements on many citation types that, at least by manual evaluations, show promise. However, we also found mismatches, as in the example

where “Williamson (1987) raises questions in response to another article, while the model suggested that the present article disputed the argument. The Swedish example clearly uses authority arguments when arguing that “the very well noted study about...”, while in the German example, the model mistakes ‘data source’ with a model, which is not that far from a correct idea.

Table 3. Example sentences from research articles with a prediction score and matched citation category

Citation type	Score	Statement
Relevant:		
Authority	0.40	Using results from psychological research, Eckel and Wilson (1999) have stated that ‘it might be argued that the rational agents in standard game theoretic models are autistic
Critiques	0.24	The problems with all these explanations are well-known. First, they reduce the agents to, more or less, cultural or structural ‘dupes’ (Giddens, 1984).
Data source	0.34	However, in the literature there are numerous examples where this does not occur, in both b-cells [Karaskov et al., 2006] and islets [Elouil et al., 2007], and our article adds to these observations.
Uses conclusions from	0.41	To this end, we have employed word vectors generated by means of the GloVe word embedding algorithm (see Pennington et al., 2014)
Recommended reading	0.38	A citance is in this work regarded as a contiguous sequence of sentences in the context of a citation (cf. the definition provided by Nakov et al., 2004)
Mismatch		
Disputes	0.23	Williamson (1987) raises questions about this notion in responding to Edgington (1985), who invokes the notion in addressing Fitch’s paradox of knowability.
Swedish example:		
Authority	0.23	“Ett exempel är Gloria Ladson-Billings (1995) mycket uppmärksammade publikation om vikten av kulturellt relevant undervisning”
German example		
Data source	0.36	“Informationsverarbeitungskapazität kann das Elaboration Likelihood Modell von Petty und Cacioppo (1986) erklären”

4. Discussion and Conclusions

In this study, we aimed to investigate how synthetic data can supplement smaller datasets and construct more significant amounts of data for training classification models. We applied the idea to generate variations of citation context phrases, which were then used to develop a model for citation context analysis. We find that even a limited number of statements provides a basis for potentially robust analyses, and we intend to develop the technique further. Among other things, we aim to optimise the classifier and investigate the amount of data needed to generate continuously robust classifications. An interesting observation was that the model is multilingual and, upon visual inspection, performs relatively well on citation statements in different languages. Here, it is tested in Swedish and German. This is a significant advancement, as it is often argued that internationalisation can only occur if researchers publish in English. Still, our initial analyses indicate that the automated language model can classify text regardless of language. One aspect we have yet to explore is that citation contexts are rarely uniform but often serve multiple functions in scientific text. We only chose to let the model assign probabilities for one class per example, but it is possible to assign multiple classes if the strength of the match exceeds a threshold for more than one class.

While these results show promise for using various generative and transformer-based language models, such as Claude and Sentence-BERT, to solve classification problems within bibliometrics, there are several routes for future exploration. Further experimentation with real-time scenarios and human evaluators can help us better understand how the classifier performs in real-world research situations. Additionally, exploring more refined techniques for citation context typing and role classification remains an area of interest for future research.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates the potential of integrating different AI- and language models to enhance citation context typing and analysis of research content. By combining LLM algorithms and synthetic data generation techniques, we propose a novel approach to machine learning in scientometric research where training data is often scarce. The opportunities of extending these analyses to multilingual settings show potential for further work.

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